

IMPACT BEHAVIOR OF CERAMIC MATRIX
COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Ceramic and ceramic matrix composites with continuous SiC fibers in a lithium aluminosilicate matrix were tested in a low blow instrumented impact apparatus. The composite architectures were unidirectional (0°) and crossply ($0/90^\circ$). An early development laminate with a borosilicate glass matrix and graphite fibers was also tested. The fiber-matrix frictional sliding mechanism which is responsible for improved ceramic matrix composite static toughness is also operative at elevated loading rates. Also the impact toughness of these composites is much greater than for their monolithic ceramic matrix.

INTRODUCTION

Ceramics have found only limited use in modern structural applications, primarily as a result of their low toughness and poor tensile behavior. The development of processing methods for tough high tensile strength ceramic composites has led to a resurgence of interest in the use of ceramics for structural purposes [1-3]. In ceramic composites exhibiting tough behavior and high tensile strength, strong fibers remain intact during matrix fracture, resulting in periodic matrix cracks and a post-cracking load sustaining capability. It has been shown that the bond between fiber and matrix, in tough composites, is weak, and energy is absorbed, during crack propagation by frictional sliding of the fiber through the matrix [4]. In unidirectionally reinforced composites, the matrix cracking stress, the interfacial frictional sliding resistance and the composite ultimate stress are characteristic stresses and are not sensitive to matrix damage, because the fibers have sufficient strength to support the load in the presence of the matrix cracks.

Properly processed composites, therefore, exhibit the damage tolerant behavior which is imperative if ceramic composites are to find application in structures subjected to tensile loading [5,6]. Unfortunately, the low fiber-matrix bond strength important in these composites results in inferior transverse properties. As is the case in the reinforced epoxy composites, such considerable anisotropy can be overcome by the use of laminates. Recent investigations of the tensile and compressive response of symmetric ($0/90^\circ$) laminated SiC reinforced lithium aluminosilicate glass ceramics have shown that the stress-strain characteristics of these laminates are predictable, based on strength measurements for the individual laminate layers in combination with knowledge of residual stresses present in the matrix [7,8]. Although the mechanical response of continuous fiber reinforced ceramic matrix composites (CMC's) is being extensively studied under conditions of static loading, little information is available about their response to impact or dynamic loading. In particular, it is not known whether the fiber-matrix frictional sliding mechanism responsible for ceramic composite toughness is operative at elevated loading rates. This paper describes the response of unidirectional and symmetric ceramic laminate composites subjected to instrumented impact loading.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

LAS III glass was utilized to provide a comparison between ceramic and CMC materials. LAS III has a modified Corning 9608 matrix. The basic lithium aluminosilicate matrix was modified with a nucleating agent and the addition of refractory oxides and metals to provide for characteristics such as, fiber barrier layers and high temperature oxidation resistance in the composites.

An early development laminate CMC material was provided from United Technologies Research Center (UTRC). It consisted of a borosilicate glass matrix with 50 v/o graphite fibers. The 5 micron fibers were in 200 micron $0/90^\circ$ crossply bundles.

The other CMC materials were also from UTRC. The basic composition was the LAS III matrix with Nicalon SiC fibers. The fiber diameter was 15 microns. The architectures were unidirectional (0°) and crossply ($0/90^\circ$). The $0/90^\circ$ crossply bundles were 200 microns thick. In addition a composite was fabricated from bolts of SiC woven into 29 x 29 12 harness satin weave (HSW) fabric. The 29 x 29 refers to the number of warp ends per inch and the 12 is the fill picks per inch. The architecture of this composite is essentially $0/90^\circ$, and the crossply bundle thickness is also 200 microns. Typical CMC micro structures are given in figure 1.

The impact specimen had a span of 40 mm and a width of 10 mm. Due to the available panel thickness, the base dimension was less than 10 mm which is the prescribed Charpy geometry. The a/W was 0.2 with a notch tip radius of 178 microns. Relative to the fiber direction for the 0° material and the long panel dimension for the $0/90^\circ$ material, L-T and T-L specimens were tested.

FIGURE 1. CMC MICROSTRUCTURES. (A) LAS III/SiC-0°; (B) LAS III/SiC-0/90°; (C) LAS III SiC-HSW, AND (D) BOROSILICATE GLASS/GRAPHITE-0/90°

A low blow instrumented Charpy impact test machine was utilized for testing. The test velocity was 0.5 m/s, while some tests were performed at a velocity of 1.78 m/s. The test temperature was 20°C.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The impact force-time curves for the ceramic and CMC materials are depicted in figure 2. Noting that time is related to deflection, figure 2(b) for LAS III and the LAS III/SiC CMC's illustrates the excellent deflection capability of the composites compared to monolithic ceramics. The force-time response is similar to that described for axial tensile tests [1,5] which includes the initial elastic response of the combined matrix and fiber, followed by periodic matrix cracking and then a region while the fibers bridge the cracks to take up the stress to the maximum load where fiber bundle failure occurs and finally the energy to complete fracture is increased by the frictional resistance of fiber pull-out from the matrix. This behavior is best illustrated by the LAS III/SiC 0/90° curve of figure 2(b).

The absorbed impact energy per unit area values for all the materials are given in table 1. These values are for L-T orientation specimens. Although there were slight differences in the load-time impact curves between L-T and T-L orientation specimens, the absorbed impact energy data were essentially the same.

TABLE 1

Absorbed impact energy per unit area values for ceramic and ceramic matrix composites.

<u>Material</u>	Impact Velocity, m/s	Absorbed Impact Energy per unit area, J/cm ²
LAS III	0.51	0
Borosilicate/50 v/0 Graphite 0/90°	0.53	0.65
	1.78	0.54
LAS III/46 v/0 SiC fibers -0°	0.51	14.0*
LAS III/44 v/0 SiC fibers -0/90°	0.51	6.5
LAS III/43 V/0 SiC fibers -HSW	0.53	4.9

*Specimens did not fracture into two pieces.

The highest absorbed energy value per unit area of 14 J/cm² was observed for the L-T orientation LAS III/SiC-0° CMC which has zero impact energy absorption in the T-L orientation. The 14 J/cm² impact

(A) BOROSILICATE GLASS/50 v/o GRAPHITE FIBERS-0/90°

(B) LAS III AND LAS III/44 v/o SiC FIBERS VARIOUS ARCHITECTURES

FIGURE 2. IMPACT FORCE-TIME CURVES FOR CERAMIC AND CMC MATERIALS

energy value is five times that reported by Brennan and Prewo [2] earlier for LAS I/50 v/0 SiC-0° materials. Thus, changes in the glass matrix/SiC interface and higher quality matrix and fiber materials have provided toughness improvements.

Fractography further illustrated the above observations. For example, matrix cracking and ejection, and fiber pullout are seen in figure 3(a). Figure 3(b) shows essentially little matrix fiber bonding by the extensive delamination and fiber pullout. The fractograph in figure 3(b) also explains why the LAS III/SiC-0° material was twice as tough as the 0/90° architecture material. It shows that for the same volume fraction only half the fibers can contribute to the frictional pullout contribution to the toughness.

(A) OPTICAL

(B) SEM

FIGURE 3. MACROFRACTOGRAPHS OF LAS III/44v/0 SiC FIBER-0/90° ORIENTATION

The borosilicate/graphite fiber material exhibited some impact absorption resistance. The material at the test velocity of 0.53 m/s has brittle low energy impact force-time characteristics, as shown in figure 2(a). At the higher velocity of 1.78 m/s, the inertia peak has become dominant. Also, the fracture strength has decreased owing to the finite response time of the electronic system to determine the actual tup load. Further, for low impact energy absorption materials, such as, ceramics Lueth [9] and Abe [10] state that instrumented Charpy tests can not accurately delineate the energy contributions to the impact toughness. The value of absorbed energy in table 1 for a velocity of 1.78 m/s, therefore, is questionable.

It is noted that the detailed analysis of Abe [10] for the various contributions to the observed instrumented impact energy was applied to the LAS III/SiC-0/90° curve. It was determined that the specimen elastic strain energy is not masked by the stored elastic strain energy in the machine, and thus the absorbed impact values in table 1, especially for the LAS CMC's are meaningful. Also, the test velocity was low enough to avoid the high inertia energy contribution and insufficient tup load response problems noted previously.

Abe [10] noted that even for ceramics instrumented impact tests can provide fracture related parameters, such as, fracture strength and toughness (K_I). These values are given in table 2. While the fracture toughness estimates, K_Q , are only useful from a comparative viewpoint, the K_Q values indicate that CMC's are tougher than monolithic ceramics.

TABLE 2

Fracture strengths and toughness estimates, K_Q , for ceramic and ceramic matrix composites

<u>Material</u>	<u>Fracture Strength</u> <u>(MPa)</u>	<u>K_Q</u> <u>MPa·m^{1/2}</u>
LAS III	89	8
Borosilicate/graphite fiber	142	16
LAS III/SiC fiber -0°	244	32
LAS III/SiC fiber -0/90°	240	31
LAS III/SiC fiber -HSW	206	24

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The fiber-matrix frictional sliding mechanism which is responsible for laminated ceramic matrix composite static toughness is also operative at elevated loading rates. Also, the impact toughness

of these composites is much greater than for their monolithic ceramic matrix. Modifications of the glass matrix to LAS III, changes in the matrix fiber interface and higher quality matrix and fiber materials have provided toughness improvements over earlier lithium aluminosilicate matrix/SiC fiber composites.

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